

On-animal sensor technologies and their application in sheep production: A systematic review

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Abstract

In this age of digital revolution, technological innovations are reaching across a variety of farming industries. Digital applications have been identified as a key method to improve farming efficiency; this is particularly attractive considering the increased pressure being placed on farmers to provide food to an ever-growing population. One farming industry, extensive sheep production, is yet to experience the full effects of the digital revolution but the potential is enormous. A systematic review was conducted to examine how existing on-animal sensor technology has been applied in sheep production systems. The review highlighted an increase in the number of studies being published in this subject area, with studies being conducted across a variety of countries, climates and seasons.

Background

Sensor technology such as very-high frequency (VHF) transmitters and Global Positioning System (GPS) were first used to track wildlife in the 1960s and 1990s, respectively (Kochanny, Delgiudice, & Fieberg, 2009; Swain, Friend, Bishop-Hurley, Handcock, & Wark, 2011; Turner, Udal, Larson, & Shearer, 2000). At the same time, technologies that monitor body movement were also being developed, including mercury tilt switches that monitor changes in body position and accelerometers to indicate movement based on changes in acceleration (Alvarenga et al., 2016; Champion, Rutter, & Penning, 1997; Rutter, Champion, & Penning, 1997). Over the years, continued innovation in sensor technology has provided unique opportunities for monitoring of animal behaviour. It is now widely acknowledged that novel adaptations of these technologies could provide solutions to a growing number of challenges faced by livestock producers.

A systematic review was undertaken to quantify how sensor technology has been applied in sheep research. The objective was to determine what sensors had been applied to sheep and in what research context. The preliminary results of the review will be presented.

Methods

A search of four electronic databases (Scopus, Science Direct, CAB Abstracts and ProQuest) was conducted in February 2017. Search terms included 'sheep', 'ovine', '*ovis aries*', 'ewe*', 'ram' and 'lamb' in conjunction with 'GPS', 'Global Positioning System*', 'GNSS', 'Global Navigation Satellite System*', 'accelerometer*', 'proximity log*', and 'contact log*'. Review articles, conference papers, books and book chapters were excluded, as were articles not written in English. All papers were required to include *Ovis aries* as subjects and at least one type of on-animal autonomous sensor. Once all database results had been evaluated, a bibliographic search of the relevant papers was also conducted.

A comprehensive list of criteria for each publication was then extracted, including various aspects of the methodology, the study site, the animals involved and the sensors used. The broad focus of the study was also determined based on the following criteria (Table 1).

Table 1. Defining criteria for establishing the broad focus of studies

Broad Focus	Definition
Behaviour	Use sensor data output to analyse various behaviour patterns, usually associated with a particular context e.g. lambing, grazing.
Health	Experiments that aim to identify various attributes associated with the onset of existing or potential clinical/subclinical disease and/or general indication of good health.
Rangeland Management	Focus on sheep production in a broader context to understand the impact of production on the environment.
Sensor Validation	Experiments that aim to endorse the use of sensors for various research purposes, including those that aimed to confirm the actual attachment of sensors does not impact behaviour.
Methods Validation	Focus on the sensor output data and validating methods for analysis, usually with field data.
Other	Unable to be defined by another category.

Results

A total of 869 articles were identified through the database and bibliographic searches. Approximately 17.7% (n = 154) of articles were excluded as they were relevant to sheep but not sensors. Conversely, 22.0% (n = 191) were excluded as relevant to sensors but not sheep. A total of 29.9% (n = 260) were considered not relevant to either sheep or sensors and 16.7% (n = 110) were excluded as the wrong document type. A small number of papers were also excluded as they included wild sheep species such as Bighorn sheep and mouflon (3.7%; n = 32), were not written in English (2.6%; n = 23), included sensors that were not attached to the animal e.g. handheld GPS (1.6%; n = 14) or did not have a sheep focused outcome e.g. used sheep as models for human benefit (1.3%; n = 11). Another 10 articles (1.2%) could not be retrieved and five were excluded for incomplete methodology (0.5%).

The 59 articles that met the required criteria presented 66 independent experiments published between 1983 and 2017 (Figure 1). Experiments were conducted on all continents, except Antarctica, and in a variety of climates and seasons. The majority of experiments included *Ovis aries* as the only species (75.8%; n = 50). The remaining experiments included either one (18.2%; n = 12) or two (6.1%; n = 4) additional species, with cattle being the most common addition (n = 10).

Figure 1. The number of publications published per year between 1983 and 2017 meeting the required criteria. An extrapolation of publications based on the number published between January and February 2017 is also included (dashed line).

Most experiments were conducted using a single sensor (77.3%; n = 51), followed by two sensors (16.7%; n = 11) and three sensors (6.0%; n = 4). GPS was the most commonly used sensor (n = 39), followed by motion sensors (n = 23) and jaw/bite sensors (n = 10). Attachment was most commonly through use of a collar (n = 42) or harness (n = 25).

Discussion

This review highlights the relatively wide application of sensors across a number of sheep production contexts. The popularity of sensors appears to be increasing, with an increasing number of studies being published in the last 30 years (Figure 1). Whilst there appears to be a drop in publications for 2017, this value only represents two months of publications as per the time of the database search. Thus if we extrapolate this value over a 12 month period, it is likely that the number published in 2017 will surpass those published in previous years.

Of the 66 experiments reviewed, GPS and motion sensors (including accelerometers, inertial monitoring units (IMUs), mercury tilt switches and inclinometers) were used in all but two experiments, either separately or in conjunction with another sensor type. This shows the popularity of these two sensors and their ability to be easily applied in sheep research. Furthermore, as the sensors record unique aspects of sheep behaviour i.e. GPS records spatial movements whereas motion sensors record body movements, it is likely that these two sensors will remain relevant for research applications.

Conclusion

The results of this review highlight the increasing application of sensor technology in sheep research. The preliminary results also highlight how patterns in sensor use have changed. As the majority of studies reviewed include sheep as the sole species, the interest in the use of these technologies in commercial sheep production is evident. Thus, as more research is conducted, commercialisation of the technology will become more achievable.

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